

Lost and Found: The Unexpected Journey of an Ingested Fish bone

MUHAMMAD SYAFIQ BIN MOHD KHAIRUL¹, KUHAN KANAGARATNAM²,
WAN AHMAD AMIRUDDIN WAN HASSAN³, HAFIZ BIN MOHAMAD MAHBOB⁴

1. OTORHINOLARYNGOLOGY HEAD AND NECK SURGERY, ADVANCE WOUND CARE UNIT, HOSPITAL SULTAN ISMAIL JOHOR BAHRU, JOHOR BAHRU, MYS 2. Otolaryngology - Head and Neck Surgery, HOSPITAL SULTAN ISMAIL, johor bahru, MYS 3. Otorhinolaryngology Head and Neck Surgery, HOSPITAL SULTAN ISMAIL, JOHOR BAHRU, MYS 4. Otolaryngology - Head and Neck Surgery, HOSPITAL SULTAN ISMAIL JOHOR BAHRU, JOHOR BAHRU, MYS

Corresponding author: MUHAMMAD SYAFIQ BIN MOHD KHAIRUL, syfqkhr@gmail.com

Abstract

A 62-year-old gentleman presented with a foreign body sensation on the left side of his throat following accidental fish bone ingestion. Initial symptoms of odynophagia improved over several days, but he later developed left-sided neck swelling. Examination and imaging confirmed the presence of an extraluminal foreign body. An open neck exploration via trans-cervical approach was performed to remove the fish bone. This case highlights the diagnostic challenges in identifying and managing extraluminal foreign bodies in the neck.

Categories: Emergency Medicine, General Surgery, Otolaryngology

Keywords: ingestion, migration, fishbone, head and neck surgery, foreign body

Introduction

Accidental ingestion of fish bones is a common occurrence, particularly in cultures where fish is a dietary staple. While most ingested foreign bodies pass through the gastrointestinal tract without incident, complications can arise when they become lodged, (Apfelbaum et al., 2013) [1]. This case report details a unique presentation of an extraluminal fish bone causing a neck abscess, emphasizing the importance of thorough diagnostic evaluation and appropriate surgical intervention.

Case Presentation

Case Presentation:

A 62-year-old gentleman with no significant past medical history presented to the Otorhinolaryngology clinic after ingesting a fish bone eight days prior. He initially experienced a foreign body sensation on the left side of his throat accompanied by odynophagia. These symptoms gradually improved, but three days before his clinic visit, he developed swelling on the left side of his neck.

On examination, the patient's general condition was stable. He was ambulatory, and his vital signs were within normal ranges. Neck examination revealed a firm, 2x2 cm mass at the left level II and III, adjacent to the hyoid bone. The mass was slightly tender to palpation, but there were no overt skin changes. Range of motion in the neck was full.

A plain lateral neck Xray was done, there was no foreign body visualised, as can be seen in Figure 1.

A flexible laryngoscopic examination using Ambu® aScope™ revealed pooling of purulent discharge in the left vallecula, although no foreign body or medialization of the pharyngeal walls was detected. Due to the high clinical suspicion of a retained foreign body. A contrast-enhanced neck CT scan was ordered, which identified the presence of an extra-luminal foreign body adjacent to left lateral aspect of hyoid bone as shown in Figure 2.

(Figure 1)

FIGURE 1: Lateral neck Xray- showing negative findings- no foreign body visualised

(Figure 2)

FIGURE 2: Multiplane CT image Visualising location of hyperdense Foreign body with surrounding area of hypodensity suggestive of collection/exudate

Based on the CT findings, the decision was made to perform neck exploration via a transcervical approach to retrieve the foreign body and address the abscess.

A 7 cm skin incision on the neck swelling, parallel to the Langer lines, was made, as shown in Figure 3. The neck was opened by layers, and the subplatysmal flap was raised. Upon tunneling towards the hyoid bone, small area of collection with minimal slough were noted. After draining and gentle de-sloughing, the tip of the fish bone was soon identified, as can be seen in Figure 4. It was gently pulled out parallel to its axis to minimize trauma. Upon thorough probing and examination, no fistula communicating to the lumen of the larynx was observed. The area was washed, and the neck wound was closed in layers.

(Figure 3)

FIGURE 3: Image shows surgical marking and planning prior incision, area of swelling marked with dotted line, just below the Hyoid bone marked as "H"

(Figure 4)

FIGURE 4: Image shows a burried Fish Bone (marked with the green arrow)

(Figure 5)

FIGURE 5: The fish bone extracted- measuring 3cm in length

Post-operatively, the patient showed significant improvement in symptoms. The neck swelling resolved, and the purulent discharge from valleculae subsided. The patient was discharged with antibiotics (T. cefuroxime 500mg BD) and follow-up appointments to monitor recovery. During routine follow up a week post operative, patient was well, the neck wound was healed, Flexible Laryngoscopic examination using Ambu® aScope™, findings was unremarkable and showed normal anatomy with no evidence of residual infection or foreign body. Suture on skin was removed and patient was discharged from our service.

Discussion

Foreign body ingestion can lead to a range of complications, from minor mucosal abrasions to life-threatening conditions such as perforations and abscesses (Brook, 2009; Marx, 2020) [2,3]. A prospective study by Ngan et al. involving 358 patients showed that fish bone impaction led to perforations in up to 4% of cases, reinforcing the potential severity of such events (Ngan et al., 1990) [4]. This case illustrates the importance of maintaining a high index of suspicion for retained foreign bodies even when initial symptoms appear to improve. Normal endoscopic findings in a symptomatic patient should always raise the suspicion of a migrated fish bone (Koh et al., 2021) [5]. The extraluminal migration of the fish bone in this patient underscores the need for comprehensive imaging and prompt surgical intervention. It is also noted that a negative finding on simple plain radiography does not exclude the diagnosis of foreign body ingestion (Erbil et al., 2013) [6].

Similar cases have been documented where foreign bodies have migrated extraluminally, leading to abscess formation and necessitating surgical removal (Sanghvi, Gupta, & Gandhoke, 2019) [7]. Thuduvage et al. (2021) described a comparable case requiring transcervical exploration after migration into the soft tissues of the neck [8]. This case adds to the body of literature by highlighting the diagnostic challenges and the effectiveness of a transcervical approach in managing such cases. Also, comparative cases where simple X-ray and scope procedures were found inadequate, and the need for Computed Tomography Neck was necessary to identify and locate the ingested foreign body (Hussain et al., 2022) [9]. Yew et al. (2024) emphasized the value of serial CT imaging in accurately tracing FB migration across tissue planes [10].

Prevention of impacted throat foreign body (FB) involves education and behavioral precautions. In children, supervision and age-appropriate toys are essential (Kay & Gungor, 2012) [11]. Adults, especially the elderly or those with neurological issues, should avoid talking while eating, chew thoroughly, and ensure proper denture fitting (Chapple & Rohatgi, 2021) [12]. Habitual practices like holding pins or toothpicks in the mouth should be discouraged. Public awareness and early medical evaluation after suspected ingestion are key to avoiding complications (Nwaorgu et al., 2004) [13]. Ambe et al. (2012) further highlighted that patient education and early intervention are critical in reducing hospital admissions and complications [14].

Conclusions

This case emphasizes the need for vigilance in patients presenting with a history of foreign body ingestion, even if initial symptoms appear to improve. A combination of clinical examination, flexible laryngoscopy, and advanced imaging modalities is essential for accurate diagnosis. A clinician needs to trust the patient and suspect a migratory foreign body in the case of persistent symptoms despite negative scope findings. Early surgical intervention can prevent complications and ensure a better prognosis.

Additional Information

Disclosures

Human subjects: Informed consent for treatment and open access publication was obtained or waived by all participants in this study. **Conflicts of interest:** In compliance with the ICMJE uniform disclosure form, all authors declare the following: **Payment/services info:** All authors have declared that no financial support was received from any organization for the submitted work. **Financial relationships:** All authors have declared that they have no financial relationships at present or within the previous three years with any organizations that might have an interest in the submitted work. **Other relationships:** All authors have declared that there are no other relationships or activities that could appear to have influenced the submitted work.

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References

1. Apfelbaum, J. L., Hagberg, C. A., Caplan, et al.: Practice guidelines for management of the difficult airway: an updated report by the American Society of Anesthesiologists Task Force on Management of the Difficult Airway. *Anesthesiology*. 118:251-270.
2. Brook, I. (2009): Microbiology and management of neck abscesses in children . *Journal of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery*. 67:1165-1170.
3. Marx, J. (2020): *Rosen's emergency medicine: Concepts and clinical practice*. Elsevier Health Sciences .
4. Ngan JH, Fok PJ, Lai EC, et al.: A prospective study on fish bone ingestion . Experience of 358 patients. *Ann Surg*. 1990, 211:459-462. [10.1097/0000658-199004000-00012](https://doi.org/10.1097/0000658-199004000-00012)
5. Koh, W. J., Lum, et. al: Extraluminal migration of ingested fish bone in the upper aerodigestive tract: A series of three cases with broad clinical spectrum of manifestations and outcomes. *International journal of otolaryngology and head and neck surgery*. 89:106606.
6. Erbil B, Karaca MA, Aslaner MA, et al.: Emergency admissions due to swallowed foreign bodies in adults . *World J Gastroenterol*. 2013, 19:6447-6452. [10.3748/wjg.v19.i38.6447](https://doi.org/10.3748/wjg.v19.i38.6447)
7. Sanghvi, S., Gupta, N., & Gandhoke, C. S. (2019): Clinical and microbiological profile of head and neck space infections in a tertiary care center. *Indian Journal of Otolaryngology and Head and Neck Surgery*. 71:476-481.
8. Thuduvage VS: Migrated fish bone into the neck: a case report . *J Med Case Rep*. 2021, 15:441. [10.1186/s13256-021-02968-2](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13256-021-02968-2)
9. Hussain, S. Z. M., Kk, et al.: Migratory Foreign Bodies in the Aerodigestive Tract: The Importance of CT Imaging. *Cureus*. 14:21595-10. [10.7759/cureus.21595](https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.21595)
10. Yew, T.T., Tang, et al.: Guide to extraluminal fish bone retrieval with serial computed tomography . *J Med Case Rep*. 2024, 18:419. [10.1186/s13256-024-04719-5](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13256-024-04719-5)
11. Kay, M., & Gungor, A. (2012): Pediatric foreign body aspiration: Current challenges and strategies for prevention and management. *Clinical Pediatric Emergency Medicine*. 13:115-121.
12. Chapple, A., & Rohatgi, S. (2021): Foreign bodies in the upper aerodigestive tract: Prevention and management. *ENT Journal*. 100:80-85.
13. Nwaorgu, O. G., Onakoya, et al.: Esophageal impacted dentures. *Journal of the National Medical Association*. 96:1350-1353.
14. Ambe P, Weber SA, Schauer M, Knoefel WT: Swallowed foreign bodies in adults: Incidence, clinical characteristics and management. *Dtsch Arztebl Int*. 2012, 109:869-875. [10.3238/arztebl.2012.0869](https://doi.org/10.3238/arztebl.2012.0869)